

The Implementation of Green Recruitment and Selection in Increasing the Competitive Advantage of Jatiluwih Tourism Village

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ABSTRACT: This article examines the implementation of green recruitment & selection (GRS) in increasing the competitive advantage of the Jatiluwih tourism village, Tabanan, Bali, Indonesia. The data used in discussing this article are qualitative and quantitative data through observation, interviews, and literature study. Informants are determined by snowball sampling technique. Informants who were interviewed were 9 people involving 30 respondents. Respondents were selected by random sampling of employees working in tourism villages. Data analysis used a combination of qualitative and quantitative descriptive. The results of the study show that green recruitment & selection (GRS) in increasing the competitive advantage of the Jatiluwih tourism village has been going very well. This is evidenced by the results of community opinion data processing which states that GRS in increasing the competitive advantage of the Jatiluwih tourism village is at an average score of 4.30 (very good). This shows that the green recruitment & selection that has been implemented by the management can maintain a sustainable tourism village so that it continues to exist. For this reason, the management is expected to continue to carry out green recruitment and selection on an ongoing basis so that the tourism village still has a competitive advantage in the future.

KEYWORDS: implementation, green recruitment, green selection, competitive advantage, tourism village

INTRODUCTION

Jatiluwih tourism village is one of the tourist villages which is included in the category of advanced tourism villages in Tabanan Regency. This tourist village has a lot of potential resources, both natural resource potential and artificial resources that are attractive for tourists to visit. Cooper (2011) stated that the feasibility of developing a tourism village is linked to the concept of tourism product components consisting of: attractions, amenities, access, ancillary services, retailing and order services. Therefore, in the development of this tourist village, it is necessary to consider the various potentials that exist to support the development of tourism in the village. Garrod, (2012) argues that there are two approaches related to the application of planning principles in the context of tourism development, namely the approach associated with planning systems that emphasize potential benefits and secondly tend to be associated with participatory planning cores that are more centralized with provisions and arrangements that are more balanced between development and tourism. controlled planning.

In the development of sustainable tourism it is aimed at developing local potential originating from nature, socio-culture or the economy in order to contribute to local government, as well as improve people's welfare. Reid, et.al (2004); Gelbman, Timothy, (2011); and Nunkoo, et.al (2012) said that in developing tourism, it is necessary to develop a model of balance between economic, environmental, socio-cultural benefits and community empowerment. In an effort to empower the community, the most important thing that needs to be socialized from the start is that tourism activities apart from having a positive impact on local communities must also make a direct contribution to environmental conservation, as happened in Jatiluwih village. Pugra, et.al (2011) stated that the impact of tourism development has been able to create job opportunities for the community through the opening of various types of businesses related to tourism that can be utilized by the workforce. The emergence of these job opportunities has motivated local people to get involved in the world of tourism.

Therefore the motivation of the local workforce is a key factor in the development of tourist villages. Human resource management practices play a crucial role in shaping organisational behavior and culture (Obie, et.al 2025). The motivation of the local workforce in village management is very influential on the image so that it can increase the competitive advantage of tourist villages. This image will directly determine the sustainability of the tourist village. Every tourist village member always tries to develop a positive image and minimize negative images (Labato, et.al, 2006); Putra, Pitana (2010); (Darmayanti & Oka,

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2020) This means that in the development of a tourist village must pay attention to the sustainability of the components of sustainable tourism, such as: environmental, economic, social, and cultural aspects of the local community. It is hoped that the development of the Jatiluwih tourism village will be able to optimally empower the local workforce so that this tourist village can be sustainable. The good or bad image will directly determine the development or not of the development of the tourism village in the future. Every tourist destination must always try to develop a positive image and minimize negative images (Hernandes-Labato, (2006); Oka, et.al (2021a). The image obtained from the tourism village does not only rely on elements from natural resources but is seen from how the manager is able to empower local workers in managing the tourism village in order to be able to face challenges that may occur in the future. For this reason, this article focuses on examining the implementation of green recruitment & selection in increasing the competitive advantage of the Jatiluwih tourism village from the perspective of employees.

METHODOLOGY

The discussion of this article uses qualitative and quantitative data. Data collection was carried out through observation, in-depth interviews, and literature study. Data from informants' opinions were taken from local people who understand the implementation of green recruitment and selection in tourist villages. Key informants were determined using a purposive sampling method. In-depth interviews were conducted with informants (community leaders). The first informant was taken from a community leader, then a search for other informants was carried out based on the instructions from the first informant, and so on. When the answers are saturated data collection is stopped. Data were analyzed descriptively qualitatively, through processing and interpreting data which is a series of activities of reviewing, grouping, systematizing, interpreting and reifying data so that a phenomenon has social, academic and scientific value (Bungin 2020).

Furthermore, to obtain data on community opinion in the implementation of green recruitment and selection, a number of questionnaires were distributed. Distribution of questionnaires using random sampling method to employees who work in tourist villages (Sugiyono 2022). The number of samples was quoted as many as 30 respondents. To study people's perception of the implementation of green recruitment and selection in this tourist village, quantitative descriptive using a Likert scale is used. The research design is limited to explaining the implementation of green recruitment and selection in Jatiluwih village using a combined analysis of both qualitative and quantitative. Respondents filled out a questionnaire, which contained an assessment of people's perceptions in implementing green recruitment and selection referring to opinions Govindarajulu, Daily (2004) by giving a score of 1 to 5, then analyzed using a Likert scale. Kusmayadi & Sugiarto (2000) stated that the Likert scale is a tool for measuring community opinion, which is measured from a very positive to very negative level, to indicate their level of agreement or disagreement with the statements outlined in the questionnaire. The measurement results were analyzed using a scale of 4.20 - 5.00 (very good), 3.40 - 4.19 (good), 2.60 - 3.39 (fairly good), 1.80 - 2.59 (poor) , 1.00 - 1.79 (very less). It is hoped that this measurement can reveal community employees in implementing green recruitment and selection in this village.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In managing a tourist village, management skills are needed in managing human resources so that it can be sustainable. Management's ability to manage sustainable human resources is often referred to as Green Human Resource Management (GHRM). GHRM integrates environmentally friendly human resource (HR) initiatives and practices for the sustainable use of resources which results in more efficiency, reduces the amount of waste, and increases a caring attitude at work (Margaretha & Saragih, 2013). Furthermore, Adhikari et al. (2014) defines GHRM is the implementation of HR management policies and practices for the sustainable use of resources in organizations and promotes environmental sustainability. According to Arulrajah et al. (2016) GHRM is defined as the process of making employees' mindsets more green by using "green" human resource policies and practices. This is for the benefit of the individual, society and the environment. The human resource management function is to act as a driver of sustainability by implementing GHRM policies and practices with the aim of improving environmental performance. Today, the concept of GHRM promotes greater awareness among companies, private/public sector, seeking to implement the role of GHRM activities in strengthening and driving environmental performance. GHRM's commitment will help reduce environmental degradation activities and protect the environment for present and future generations (Jackson, et.al., 2011).

An organization can promote effective and efficient GHRM by implementing green recruitment and selection (GRS), green training (GTR), and green compensation (GCO) practices (Govindarajulu & Daily (2004). In a business organization, so that the implementation of activities/operations can run smoothly, it must begin with the recruitment and selection of employees who understand green environment. Organizations should focus on selecting and recruiting employees who are supportive and interested in the environment (Renwick et al., 2013). Therefore, to increase the attractiveness of recruitment and selection for prospective employees who are increasingly aware of the importance of the environment (Ehnert, 2009), organizations must build a reputation that is inspired by the idea that this organization is responsive to the environment (Hadjri et al., 2020).

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Organizations should reflect their environmental sustainability agenda on the organization's website and other available public channels so that prospective employees can clearly see the organization's green focus. This is confirmed by the research of (Guerci, et.al, 2016) who found that intentions related to environmental sustainability can play a major role in attracting potential applicants. Green selection recruitment ensures that new recruits understand the green organizational culture and share its environmental values through selection of prospective employees' knowledge, values, and beliefs about the environment. Recruitment messages must include environmental criteria (Arulrajah, et.al, 2016). In the job analysis phase, job descriptions and job specifications must clarify and emphasize environmental aspects, green achievements and explain what is expected of "green" employees in the future (Renwick, et.al, 2013)

However, Welford (1997) recommends a number of steps that organizations can implement to enhance GHRM through a green selection recruitment process. First, the job description must include elements that emphasize the role of environmental reporting. Second, induction programs for newly recruited employees should focus on providing information about the policies, values and goals of green organizations. Third, interviews should be conducted to assess the candidate's potential suitability for the organization's greening program. The design of this interview process is supported by Hadjri, et.al (2020) who stated that when interviewing potential candidates, questions related to the environment should be a major part of the evaluation process. Arulrajah, et.al (2016) explained that organizations can increase their efforts to protect the environment through integrating environmental tasks into each employee's job duties and responsibilities, designing new jobs or positions that care about the environment to focus exclusively on the environmental performance aspects of organization. During the selection of prospective employees, the employee selection process must ensure the selection of candidates who are committed to the environment (Jabbour., 2011).

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

The people of Jatiluwih village continue to synergize in managing the tourism village so they can compete with similar tourist villages. The manager synergizes with stakeholders for the sustainability of the development of a tourist village so that it can compete competitively in the future. Village management seeks to maximize tourism potential through optimal community empowerment and minimize threats that disrupt the existence of tourist villages. Through harmonious communication, coordination and cooperation, it is expected to be able to find solutions in developing villages towards green-based tourism considering the activities in developing tourism villages are very complex. This is in line with opinion of Darmayanti, et.al (2020); Oka, et.al (2021b) which mentions that planning for the development of tourist destinations is a complex task due to the interdependence of various stakeholders and fragmented control over destination resources. Therefore, the development of sustainable tourism at the regional level requires cooperation and collaboration between relevant stakeholders so that it can be sustainable.

This article examines the application of green recruitment & selection in increasing the competitive advantage of the Jatiluwih tourist village. In the study of the application of green recruitment & selection aspects in tourist villages, they were grouped into 7 green recruitment and selection (GRS) variables adopted by opinion (Govindarajulu, Daily (2004). Meanwhile, the variable aspects of competitive advantage are represented by 3 variables as shown in Table 1. Prior to distributing the questionnaires, validity and reliability tests were carried out to test the accuracy of the research instrument in the form of a questionnaire..

1. Validity and Reliability Test

Through validity and reliability tests it is hoped that they can be used statistically so that they can measure variables in a valid and reliable manner. In the early stages of testing the questionnaire instrument was carried out on 30 respondents, referring to opinions Sugiyono, (2022) which states that in the external validity test the number of samples tested was around 30 people. The results of this validity test indicate that the 10 questions from each variable indicator outlined in the questionnaire are valid because the value of r count is > 0.30 . Furthermore, it is stated that if the correlation of each indicator is positive and the magnitude is > 0.3 then this factor is a strong construct or the instrument has good construction validity. The validity test was carried out using the SPSS for windows program for each statement item in the questionnaire classified into 2 aspects, namely: green recruitment and selection (GRS) and competitive advantage (CA).

Reliability test shows the extent to which a measurement can give results that are not different when the measurement is carried out again on the same subject. The reliability test used is for one-time data collection and for analyzing questionnaires whose scale is between 0 and 1 using the Cronbach alpha formula, where an instrument is said to be reliable with a significant level at Cronbach alpha values > 0.6 (Simamora, 2001).

Tests carried out on 2 aspects, namely: green recruitment and selection (GRS) and competitive advantage (CA). The green recruitment and selection aspect consists of 7 statements, namely: applicants have environmental knowledge (x1), choose workers who are interested in the environment (x2), job descriptions, and job specifications must clarify and emphasize environmental aspects and explain what is expected of them. future "green" employees (x3), recruitment of new employees

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focuses on providing information on organizational policies and goals (x4), management selects and hires a workforce that is supportive and committed to the environment (x5), management prioritizes local workforce in recruiting workers (x6), and green selection recruitment ensures that the recruitment of new candidates understands the green organizational culture and its various environmental values (x7). The aspects of competitive advantage include: tourism village management empowering all available resources with strategies to achieve the expected end goal (x8), competitive advantage of tourism villages in the form of natural potential (terracing rice fields, mountains); and culture (cultural heritage, subak system, customs, culinary) (x9), and competitive advantage is also seen from the quality of service, product quality and prices according to consumer demand and tastes where the company is able to survive always superior to competitors (x10).

The 10 statement items above produce a significance level of 0.919, which means that the questionnaire is reliable to be used as a research instrument. Based on the results of the validity and reliability tests, it can be concluded that the research instrument used has validity because it is able to produce good moment products and has reliability because its value is relatively consistent, which is >0.60 . With the fulfillment of the results of validity and reliability, this research still uses the instrument in the form of a questionnaire.

2. Based on the results of the questionnaire analysis distributed to 30 respondents, where the assessment uses a Likert scale. This perception assessment uses a Likert scale with the initial step of giving a score by converting strongly agree = 5, agree = 4, fairly good = 3, poor = 2, and very less = 1. Community perceptions of the implementation of green human resources in Jatiluwih village, as shown in Table 1. The results of all frequency data and analysis of all items, are described in a verbal narrative in the interpretation of each of the following variables:

Table 1. Community Perception Level in the Implementation of Green Recruitment and Selection

Aspects	Variables	Choice					Σ	Ave- rage	Criteria
		5	4	3	2	1			
Green Recruit- ment & Selection	Have knowledge about the environment (x1)	80	28	18	2	0	128	4,27	ery good
	Choose workers who are interested in the environment (x2)	90	28	9	4	0	131	4,37	ery good
	Able to clarify environmental aspects (x3)	75	28	21	2	0	126	4,20	Very good
	New employee recruitment focuses on providing information about organizational policies and objectives (x4)	95	20	15	2	0	132	4,40	ery good
	Choose a workforce that is committed to environment (x5)	85	28	15	2	0	130	4,33	ery good
	Prioritizing local workforce (x6)	90	28	9	2	1	130	4,33	ery good
	Recruitment of new candidates who understand green organizational culture (x7)	80	24	12	4	2	122	4,07	Good
Competi- tive Advan- tage	Management empowers all potential resources (x8)	90	24	15	2	0	131	4,37	Very good
	Has a natural and cultural competitive advantage (x9)	90	28	12	2	0	132	4,40	Very good
	Have a competitive advantage in the form of service quality, product, and price (x10)	95	20	9	2	1	127	4,23	Very good
Average								4,30	Very good

Source: Research results

An explanation of the level of community perception in implementing green recruitment and selection to increase the competitive advantage of the Jatiluwih tourism village, is further described as follows:

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1. Have knowledge about the environment (x1)

Environmental knowledge is the initial capital for prospective candidates to participate in protecting and preserving the environment. (Enhert, 2009) mentions to increase the attractiveness of recruitment and selection for prospective employees, selected from those who are increasingly aware of the importance of environmental existence. In preserving the environment, it is necessary to understand adequate knowledge to raise awareness in protecting the environment itself. This was confirmed by I Nengah Kartika (Head of Jatiluwih village); I Nengah Wirata (Manager of Yeh Baat Villa & Restaurant) who stated that in recruiting the workforce employed in the management of tourist villages are villagers who have knowledge about the environment. The informants' opinions were then cross-checked with the opinions of the respondents. The results of cross tabulation of this variable obtained a score of 4.27 (very good) meaning that job applicants accepted to work in tourist villages are those who have knowledge and awareness of the importance of the existence of the environment so that the existence of the natural environment can be enjoyed by future generations.

2. Choose workers who are interested in the environment (x2)

Environmental awareness arises from the deepest intentions. High individual intention will encourage someone to participate better in protecting the environment. Renwick, et.al (2013) stated that organizations should focus on selecting and recruiting employees who are supportive and interested in the environment. This was emphasized by I Gede Made Alitoyo (deputy manager of the tourism village); I Wayan Suarka (Head of planning & development division) who stated that in recruiting workers in tourist villages priority was given to those who had a high motivation in protecting the environment. The informants' opinions were then cross-checked with the opinions of the respondents. The results of cross tabulation of this variable obtained a score of 4.37 (very good) meaning that job applicants selected to work in tourist villages are those who are interested and have an awareness of the importance of environmental existence in the future.

3. Able to clarify environmental aspects (x3)

The job descriptions carried out in the sustainability program are the work of employees who emphasize the aspects of green environmental sustainability. The goal is that the employees involved can really understand what each individual involved in the organization will do. Renwick, et.al (2013) stated that in the job analysis phase, job descriptions and job specifications must clarify and emphasize environmental aspects, green achievements and explain what is expected of "green" employees in the future. There are several environmental aspects that need to be considered in the development of tourist destinations, such as: preservation of local tree plants, maintenance of environmental authenticity, pollution, river pollution, and others. This was confirmed by I Nengah Sutirtayasa (manager of the tourism village) who stated that in recruiting workers in tourist villages priority was given to those who had a high motivation in protecting the environment. The informants' opinions were then cross-checked with the opinions of the respondents. The results of this variable cross-tabulation obtained a score of 4.20 (very good) meaning that the job applicants selected to work in tourist villages are those who describe job specifications that emphasize environmental aspects.

4. New employee recruitment focuses on providing information about organizational policies and objectives (x4)

Provision of information about policies, values, and goals of the organization is mandatory for new employees. This aims to socialize green policies to all prospective employees for the achievement of organizational goals. Welford (1997) stated that in recruiting new employees, the focus should be on providing information about the policies, values, and goals of green organizations. The provision of information about organizational policies is carried out in a straightforward and systematic manner so that they can be easily implemented in the field. This was emphasized by Yudi Artawan (local village secretary) who stated that information about organizational policies and goals is an important factor in facilitating the attainment of organizational goals. The informants' opinions were then cross-checked with the opinions of the respondents. The results of cross-tabulation of this variable obtained a score of 4.33 (very good) meaning that in recruiting workers in tourist villages, workers who are highly committed to preserving the rural environment are needed.

5. Choose a workforce that is committed to environment (x5)

Organizational operations require highly committed human resources. Commitment is important to maintain the sustainability of an environmental work program. For this reason, in recruiting workers, it is necessary to prioritize people who have a high commitment to maintaining environmental sustainability. During the selection of prospective employees, the employee selection process must ensure the selection of candidates who are committed to the environment (Jabbour, 2011). This was confirmed by I Putu Eka Saputra (Head of promotion and marketing division) who stated that in recruiting workers in tourist villages, we look for potential workers who are committed to preserving the environment. The informants' opinions were then cross-checked with the opinions of the respondents. The results of cross tabulation of this variable obtained a score of 4.33 (very good) meaning that in recruiting workers in tourist villages, workers who are highly committed to preserving the rural environment are needed.

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6. Prioritizing local workforce (x6)

Organizational operations require strong and resilient human resources. Strong and tough means human resources who have the will, ability, and have the opportunity to devote themselves to the organization. For this reason, in recruiting workers, it is necessary to prioritize local workers, considering that they are the owners of the village. Through selective empowerment of local workers, it will encourage their awareness to be responsible for the environment in which they live. Winia, et.al (2019) states that selecting workers by prioritizing local communities can raise awareness in preserving the natural and cultural environment. This was emphasized by Ni Made Eka Endrayani (Village owned enterprise) who stated that in recruiting workers in the Jatiluwih tourist village, they still prioritize local communities to raise their awareness of the importance of protecting the environment so that tourists are increasingly visiting tourist villages. The informants' opinions were then cross-checked with the opinions of the respondents. The results of this variable cross-tabulation obtained a score of 4.33 (very good) meaning that in recruiting workers in tourist villages while still prioritizing local workers for the sustainability of tourist villages.

7. Recruitment of new candidates who understand green organizational culture (x7)

Understanding of organizational and environmental values is very important for prospective workers. The work culture in question is the ability to implement environmental preservation values so that they are sustainable. Green selection recruitment ensures that new recruits understand the culture of green organizations and share their environmental values (Jackson, et.al, 2011) through selection of knowledge, values and beliefs about the environment in an effort to maintain the existence of the environment itself. This was emphasized by I Wayan Wira Darma (Business Division) who stated that maintaining the sustainability of environmental values is an organizational culture that must be implemented by all staff involved in the organization. The informants' opinions were then cross-checked with the opinions of the respondents. The results of cross tabulation of this variable obtained a score of 4.07 (good) meaning that a green organizational culture related to green environmental values must be implemented by every employee who works in a tourist village.

8. Management empowers all potential resources (x8)

Jatiluwih Village has a number of resources to be developed into an attractive tourist attraction to visit. Some of the resources they have, namely: terracing exotic rice fields, the subak system which is a noble cultural heritage, traditional dances, and local culinary delights that are suitable for sale to tourists. This is supported by I Gede Alitoyo (deputy manager of the tourism village) who stated that this village has several interesting resources such as: cool and beautiful rice fields, a worldwide farming system, and traditional dances that are thick with traditional culture. The informants' opinions were then cross-checked with the opinions of the respondents. The results of cross-tabulation of this variable obtained a score of 4.37 (very good) meaning that these resources will be sustainable if the manager has a strategy in developing resources so that they can compete with other tourist villages.

9. Has a natural and cultural competitive advantage (x9)

The competitive advantage of a tourist village in the form of natural and cultural potential is the basic capital in developing a tourism village. These resources must be managed properly in order to become an icon of a tourist village so that it is sustainable. Murni, et.al (2023) states that the competitive advantages possessed by tourist destinations must be preserved so that they can be sustainable. This is supported by the statement of I Nengah Kartika (Head of Jatiluwih village) who stated that this competitive advantage is the capital of Jatiluwih village in the development of a tourism village. The informants' opinions were then cross-checked with the opinions of the respondents. The results of cross tabulation of this variable obtained a score of 4.40 (very good) meaning that the community stated that this competitive advantage was very important in the development of a tourism village.

10. Have a competitive advantage in the form of service quality, product, and price (x10).

Quality of service, products, and competitive prices are important components for tourists in choosing a tourist village to spend their spare time. This competitive advantage must be maintained as well as enhanced so that tourists are interested in visiting tourist villages. Porter (1987) states that competitive advantage is the value or benefit that will be paid by the buyer, by offering a lower price than competitors can bring up superior value or offering benefits to exceed the price offered. Competitive advantage in tourism village marketing is very important to be packaged properly in order to be able to attract tourist visits. This is supported by the statement of Ni Nengah Deni (Ananta Loka Restaurant) who stated that the management continues to carry out marketing both through online and offline media. The informants' opinions were then cross-checked with the opinions of the respondents. The results of cross-tabulation of this variable obtained a score of 4.23 (very good) meaning that the community thinks that tourism village marketing has been done well.

Guided by the description above, in developing Jatiluwih tourism village so that it can be sustainable it is necessary to recruit workers who have green environmental knowledge, have the motivation to preserve the environment, are committed to implementing green environmental values, are able to clarify green environment, prioritize local workers, and understand green organizational culture. Of course in the development of a sustainable tourism village, the management must involve the local community. This aims to increase community awareness in preserving nature and culture. It is also realized that community-

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based tourism development usually requires external facilitation and assistance, for this reason it is advisable to be able to establish partnerships with external entities. Various models of partnership patterns are possible, but there are also arguments for minimizing external involvement in tourism management. It is hoped that tourism management will be fully controlled, owned and managed by members of the less fortunate (marginalized) community. Various entities may engage in partnership with the management such as the private sector, NGOs and government entities (Mtapuri, Giampiccoli, 2016); (Oka, et.al, 2019) and they are expected to play different roles in the development of community-based tourism. However, the government's role is still considered fundamental in the development of community-based tourism. Governments should be the main protagonists, whose job is to formulate official definitions of forms of tourism to inform regulations and policies to the public.

CONCLUSION

Based on the description above, it can be concluded that the implementation of green recruitment & selection in increasing the competitive advantage of the Jatiluwih tourism village, Tabanan, Bali. it's been going very well. This is evidenced by the results of processing community opinion data which states that green recruitment & selection (GRS) in increasing the competitive advantage of the Jatiluwih tourism village is at an average score of 4.30 (very good). The competitive advantage possessed by this tourist village is in the form of natural potential (terracing rice fields, mountains); and culture (cultural heritage, subak system, customs, culinary) that attract tourists to visit. The competitive advantage of the tourist village is in the form of natural and cultural uniqueness that can be used as basic capital in developing a tourist village to remain the main tourist village for tourists in doing refreshments. These resources must be managed properly by the manager so that they can become an icon of a tourist village so that it is sustainable. For this reason, the management is expected to continue to carry out green recruitment and selection on an ongoing basis so that this tourist village continues to have a competitive advantage in the future.

REFERENCES

- 1) Adhikari, B., Kaehler, N., Raut, S., Marahatta, S. B., & Ggyanwali, K. (2014). Risk factors of stigma related to leprosy - A Systematic Review. *Journal of Manmohan Memorial Institute of Health Sciences*, 1(2), 3–11. <https://doi.org/10.3126/jmmihs.v1i2.9902>
- 2) Arulrajah, A. A., Opatha, H. H. D. N. P., & Nawaratne, N. N. J. (2016). Green human resource management practices: a review. *Sri Lankan Journal of Human Resource Management*, 5(1), <https://doi.org/10.4038/sljhrm.v5i1.5624>
- 3) Bungin, B. (2020). *Metode Penelitian Kualitatif. Aktualisasi Metodologis Ke Arah Ragam Varian Kontemporer*. Jakarta: PT. Raja Grafindo Persada.
- 4) Cooper, C. (2011). *Essentials of Tourism*. Mexico Oxford: Prentice Hal.
- 5) Darmayanti, P. W., & Oka, I. M. D. (2020). Implikasi Pengembangan Pariwisata Berbasis Masyarakat bagi Masyarakat di Desa Bongan. *Jurnal Ilmiah Hospitality Management*, 10(2), 142-150.
- 6) Darmayanti, P. W., Oka, I. M. D., & Sukita, I. W. (2020). Pengembangan Desa Wisata Kaba-Kaba dalam Perspektif Masyarakat Lokal. *Jurnal Ilmiah Hospitality Management*, 11(1), 15-23.
- 7) Ehnert, B. (2009). Sustainable Human Resource Management: a Conceptual and Exploratory Analysis from a Paradox Perspective.
- 8) Garrod, Brian. 2003. Local Participation in the Planning and Management of Ecotourism: A Revised Model Approach. *Journal of Ecotourism*. 2 (1). 1-21
- 9) Gelbman, A., & Timothy, D. J. (2011). Border Complexity, Tourism and International Exclaves A Case Study. *Annals of Tourism Research* 38(1):110–31.
- 10) Giampiccoli, A., Saayman, M., & Jugmohan, S. (2014). Developing Community-Based Tourism in South Africa: Addressing the Missing Link. *African Journal for Physical, Health Education, Recreation and Dance* 20(3):1139–61.
- 11) Govindarajulu, N., & Daily, B. F. (2004). Motivating employees for environmental improvement. *Industrial Management and Data Systems*, 104(3), 364–372. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02635570410530775>
- 12) Guerci, M., Longoni, A., & Luzzini, D. (2016). Translating stakeholder pressures into environmental performance – the mediating role of green HRM practices. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 27(2), 262–289. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2015.1065431>
- 13) Hadjri, M. I., Perizade, B., Zunaidah, Z., & Farla WK, W. (2020). Green Human Resource Management dan Kinerja Lingkungan: Studi Kasus pada Rumah Sakit di Kota Palembang. *Inovbiz: Jurnal Inovasi Bisnis*, 8(2), 182. <https://doi.org/10.35314/inovbiz.v8i2.1627>
- 14) Hernandez-Lobato, L., Solis-Radilla, M. M., Moliner-Tena, M. A., & SanchezGarcia, J. (2006). Tourism Destination Image, Satisfaction and Loyalty; A case study in Ixtapa-Zihuatanejo. *Mexico: Tourism Geographiec*. 8(4), 343–358.
- 15) Jackson, L. A., Von Eye, A., Witt, E. A., Zhao, Y., & Fitzgerald, H. E. (2011). A longitudinal study of the effects of Internet use and videogame playing on academic performance and the roles of gender, race and income in these

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- relationships. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 27(1), 228–239. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2010.08.001>
- 16) Jabbour, Charbel Jose Chiappetta. (2011). How green are HRM practices, organizational culture, learning and teamwork? A Brazilian study. *Industrial and Commercial Training*, 43(2), 98–105. <https://doi.org/10.1108/00197851111108926>
 - 17) Kusmayadi and Sugiarto, E. (2000). *Metodologi Penelitian Dalam Bidang Kepariwisata [Research Methodology in the Field of Tourism]*. Jakarta: PT. Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
 - 18) Labato, L. H., Radilla M.M, Tena, M.A, Garcia J. (2006). Tourism Destination Image, Satisfaction and Loyalty; A Case Study in Ixtapa-Zihuatanejo. Mexico. *Tourism Geographiec* 8(4):343–58.
 - 19) Margaretha, M., & Saragih, S. (2013). Developing new corporate culture through green human resource practice. International Conference on Business ..., March. http://www.caal-inteduorg.com/ibea2013/ejournal/059-Meily_Margaretha&Susanti_Saragih---Developing_New_Corporate_Culture.pdf
 - 20) Mtapuri, O., & Giampiccoli, A. (2016). Towards a Comprehensive Model of Community-Based Tourism Development. *South African Geographical Journal* 98(1):154–68.
 - 21) Murni, N. G. N. S., Winia, I. N., Pugra, I. W., & Oka, I. M. D. (2023). Implementation of Green Human Resource Management in Jatiluwih Tourism Destination Area. *Journal of World Science*, 2(1), 114-122.
 - 22) Nala, I.W., L., Indriani, N., & Oka, I. M. D. (2021). The Impact of Development of Pela Village as a Tourist Village in Kutai Kartanegara, East Kalimantan. *Journal of Applied Sciences in Travel and Hospitality* 4(2):85–92.
 - 23) Nunkoo, R., Ramkissoon, H., & Gursoy, D. (2012). Public Trust in Tourism Institutions. *Annals of Tourism Research* 39(3):1538–64.
 - 24) Obie, E. L., Fossung, M. F., & Ongo, N. B. E. (2025). The Impact of Green Recruitment and Selection Practices on Corporate Sustainability: Evidence from Manufacturing Companies in Cameroon. *European Journal of Management, Economics and Business*, 2(1), 57-67. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejmeb.2025.2\(1\).04](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejmeb.2025.2(1).04)
 - 25) Oka, I. M. D., Darmayanti, P. W., & Sonder, I. W. (2021a). Turtle Conservation in Serangan Island: The Implementation of Community-Based Tourism Concepts in Tourism Development. *PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology*, 18(2), 172-182.
 - 26) Oka, I. M. D., Murni, N. G. N. S., & Mecha, I. P. S. (2021b). The Community-Based Tourism at the Tourist Village in the Local People's Perspective. *GeoJournal of Tourism and Geosites*, 38(4), 988-996.
 - 27) Oka, I. M. D., Winia, I. N., & Sadia, I. K. (2019, November). The implication of the development of Serangan tourist village from the economic perspective. In *International Conference on Social Science 2019 (ICSS 2019)* (pp. 1169-1173). Atlantis Press.
 - 28) Porter, E. M. (1987). Perspectives on Strategy. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4615-6179-8>
 - 29) Pugra, I. W., Oka, I.M.D., Suparta, I. K. (2021). Kolaborasi pentahelix untuk pengembangan desa timpag menuju desa wisata berbasis green tourism. *Bhakti Persada: Jurnal Aplikasi IPTEKS*, Vol. 7 (2), p.111-120
 - 30) Putra, I. N. D., dan Pitana, I. G. (2010). *Pariwisata Pro-Rakyat Meretas Jalan Mengentaskan Kemiskinan Di Indonesia [Pro-People Tourism Paves the Way for Alleviating Poverty in Indonesia]*. Jakarta: Kementerian Kebudayaan dan Pariwisata.
 - 31) Putra, T. (2019). A Review on Penta Helix Actors in Village Tourism Development and Management. *Journal Business Hospitality and Tourism* 5(1):63–75.
 - 32) Reid, D.G., Mair, H., George, W. (2004). Community Tourism Planning a Self-Assessment Instrument. *Annals of Tourism Research* 31(3):623–39.
 - 33) Renwick, D. W. S., Redman, T., & Maguire, S. (2013). Green Human Resource Management: A Review and Research Agenda*. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 15(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2370.2011.00328.x>
 - 34) Sadia, I. K., & Oka, I. M. D. (2012). Motivasi Tenaga Kerja Bali Bekerja Di Mediterranean Shipping Company (MSC). *Jurnal Sosial Humaniora* 2(3):221–36.
 - 35) Simamora, H. (2001). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia [Human Resource Management]*. Indonesia: STIE YKPN.
 - 36) Sugiyono. (2022). *Metode Penelitian Manajemen [Management Research Methods]*. Indonesia: Alfabeta.
 - 37) Welford, R. (1997). Book Review - Richard Welford -- GREENING PEOPLE edited by Walter. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 6(1), 52–53.
 - 38) Winia, I. N., Oka, I.M.D., Pugra.I.W. (2019). The Implementation of the Community-Based Tourism at Tista Tourist Village.” In *International Conference on Applied Science and Technology 2019-Social Sciences Track (ICASTSS 2019)*. ((ICASTSS 2019)). doi: 10.2991/icastss-19.2019.15.